

DAMAGE STRENGTH OPTIMIZATION OF LAMINATES BY A RELIABILITY-BASED METHOD

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SUMMARY: This paper presents damage strength optimization of laminates using a reliability-based method. Two complementary analyses are developed: The first is a mechanical analysis of damage behavior using a thermodynamics framework which determines the failure criterion; the second is a reliability method which takes not only randomness, but also subjective uncertainties into account for failure probability calculation. This method, based on the First Order Reliability Method, requires the resolution of a constrained problem of optimization. To solve this problem, a hybrid algorithm, combining evolutionary computation techniques with deterministic procedure is presented. Filament-wound pipe optimization under pressure is discussed as a working example.

KEYWORDS: composite laminates, optimization, damage, probabilistic method, design, evolutionary algorithm, failure, reliability

INTRODUCTION

Mechanical models are generally used for designing laminated composites. Scattering and subjective uncertainties such as neglect, mistakes, incorrect modeling and manufacturing errors must be taken into consideration when designing for materials, stacking sequence, dimensions, etc.... These problems are particularly significant for composite materials. All laminate composites must perform their expected functions with a high level of reliability during the prescribed service time. Particularly, when failure may cause loss of human lives, structural reliability is indispensable. This reliability assurance is also crucially important from an economical point of view. This is why reliability-based design methodology [1,2] plays a role of vital importance in rational design.

Traditionally, structural design relies on deterministic analysis. We introduce an empirical safety factor which takes account of uncertainties in material properties, geometry and loads. In probabilistic analysis, for each failure mode, a desirable or acceptable value of reliability must be available to the designer. This reliability target is chosen using personal judgment or rational analysis. Subjective uncertainties in parameters of the laws of probability or in the type of laws are often excluded, and reliability is generally evaluated using the first order reliability index β [3]. The resulting reliability may thus be biased. Our analysis based on the principle of maximizing the probability of failure takes subjective uncertainties into account and provides a compensating alternative to this shortcoming.

FIRST DAMAGE CRITERION

In general, an N -layer laminate implies N possible layer failures, which can act as a series system or a parallel system. A series system is the lowest acceptable level for reliability ; therefore when one layer fails the laminate fails [4]. The first damage criterion is expressed in each layer. To define the damage threshold of the virgin layer, a variable definition of damage and the concept of effective stress $\tilde{\sigma}_k$ [5] applied to the k^{th} layer expressed in the fiber system (Fig. 1) is used.

Fig. 1: Fiber coordinate system

If the damage is the microcracking of the matrix, two representations of the damaged lamina can be proposed depending on the orientation chosen for the microcracks (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Two representations of the damage lamina

We can define three different types of damage:

$$D_I^k = \frac{\Delta E_2^k}{E_2^k}, \quad D_{II}^k = \frac{\Delta G_{12}^k}{G_{12}^k}, \quad D_{III}^k = \frac{\Delta G_{23}^k}{G_{23}^k} \quad (1)$$

E_2^k is Young's modulus in direction 2, and G_{12}^k and G_{23}^k the shear moduli. In fact, energetic considerations make it possible to conclude that these two representations lead roughly to the same result [6]. The evolution of the damage can be determined only by D_I^k and the relationship connecting D_{II}^k and D_{III}^k with D_I^k is:

$$\begin{cases} D_{II}^k = 1 - S_{66}^k \left[S_{66}^k + D_I^k \left(\frac{S_{11}^k S_{22}^k}{1 - D_I^k} \right)^{1/2} \right]^{-1} \\ D_{III}^k = 1 - S_{44}^k \left[S_{44}^k + D_I^k S_{22}^k \left(\frac{1}{1 - D_I^k} \right)^{1/2} \right]^{-1} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

S_{ij}^k are the compliance elements related to the engineering constants. The framework of thermodynamics [7] provides an interesting way to obtain the kinetics of the variable D_I^k . By

using this, the kinetic laws of D_I^k is a function of a variable associated with the damage, which can be defined using the free energy density. If Ψ_k is the free energy density, it can be broken down in the following way

$$\Psi_k = \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_k : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e \quad (3)$$

$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_k$ is the damage stiffness of the k^{th} layer and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$ the classical elastic strain. Then, the variable associated with the damage of the layer can be defined by

$$Y_k = \frac{\partial \Psi_k}{\partial D_I^k} \quad (4)$$

The law of evolution of the damage is defined by:

$$\dot{D}_I^k = \dot{\lambda}_k^d \frac{\partial f_k^d}{\partial Y_k} \quad (5)$$

where $\dot{\lambda}_k^d$ is the Lagrange multiplier. To obtain the law of evolution of D_I^k , a criterion of damage must be defined. We chose [8]:

$$f_k^d = |Y_k| - R_k^d - Y_k^c \leq 0 \quad (6)$$

where R_k^d indicates a hardening variable and Y_k^c represents the damage threshold of the virgin layer. Once the damage appears, the only point of interest is $R_k = 0$. The criterion can be written for $D_I^k = 0$:

$$f_k^d = |Y_k| - Y_k^c = 0 \quad (7)$$

with

$$Y_k^c = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{(\sigma_{22}^k)^2 + (\sigma_{23}^k)^2}{E_2^k} + \frac{(\sigma_{12}^k)^2}{\sqrt{E_1^k E_2^k}} \right] \quad (8)$$

where E_1^k is Young's modulus in the fiber direction. Note that Y_k^c only depends on E_1^k and E_2^k . The stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_k$ applied to the layer depends on external loads, material properties, stacking sequence and dimensions of the laminate and can be written as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_k = \mathbf{C}_k : \mathbf{R} : \mathbf{T}_k : \mathbf{R}^{-1} : \mathbf{S} : \boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad (9)$$

$\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the external stress applied to the entire laminate expressed in the laminate coordinate system, \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{T}_k are respectively the Reuter and the transformation matrix. Compliance tensor \mathbf{S} can be obtained by using the classical laminate theory. In what follows, the safety margin of the layer is

$$M_k = Y_k^c - |Y_k| \quad (10)$$

The failure set is defined by $M_k \leq 0$, and $M_k > 0$ indicates a safe state.

PROBABILISTIC METHOD

Description of the problem

The safety margin of the laminate is $M = G(\mathbf{x})$ where G is the failure function and \mathbf{x} is the vector of basic random physical variables defining the external loads, material properties, stacking sequence and dimensions of the laminate. Failure of the laminate is defined by $M \leq 0$, and $M > 0$ identifies a safe state. The fundamental problem is the computation of the probability of failure

$$P^f = \int_{M \leq 0} f_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \quad (11)$$

in which $f_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{x})$ denotes the joint probability density function of vector \mathbf{x} . The safety margin of the k^{th} lamina is $M_k = G_k(\mathbf{x})$ and its probability of failure is P_k^f . Since the laminate fails when one layer fails, the failure probability of the laminate is

$$P^f = \text{Prob} \left[\bigcup_{k=1}^N M_k \leq 0 \right] \quad (\text{approximated by Ditlevsen [9]}) \quad (12)$$

Evaluation of the damage probability of a lamina

The probability of failure of the k^{th} lamina is equal to

$$P_k^f = \int_{G_k(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0} f_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \quad (13)$$

Assuming that the probability distribution of \mathbf{x} is continuous, the variable transformation $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{x})$ then exists such that \mathbf{y} is a standardized gaussian vector of independent components [1]. The safety margin of the laminate in y -space is

$$M_k = G_k(\mathbf{x}) = G_k[\mathbf{T}^{-1}(\mathbf{y})] = g_k(\mathbf{y}) \quad (14)$$

and the failure probability is equal to

$$P_k^f = \int_{g_k(\mathbf{y}) \leq 0} \phi(\mathbf{y}) d\mathbf{y} \quad (15)$$

ϕ is the uncorrelated standard normal probability density function. Application of the First Order Reliability Method [3] implies that the failure surface of the k^{th} lamina in y -space is approximated by its tangent hyperplane in point \mathbf{y}_k^* in the surface closest to the origin. The first order reliability index β_k is defined as the minimum distance from the origin to the failure surface in y -space, i.e.

$$\mathbf{y}_k^* = \beta_k \boldsymbol{\alpha}_k \quad (16)$$

$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_k$ is the outward unit vector to the limit state surface in y -space. The first approximation of the failure probability of the lamina is

$$P_k^f \approx \Phi(-\beta_k) \quad (17)$$

where Φ is the one-dimensional standard normal cumulative distribution. Thus, the main problem is to find β_k . This is formulated as a constrained optimization problem:

$$\beta_k = \min \left[\sqrt{\mathbf{y}'\mathbf{y}} \right] \text{ subject to } \mathbf{g}_k(\mathbf{y}) = 0 \quad (18)$$

Taking into account subjective uncertainties

We make the assumption that only the vector of mean values \mathbf{m}_x is unknown. Since the vector of mean values is unknown, it is assumed that mean values have a given value \mathbf{m}_x . Now the failure probability becomes a function of \mathbf{m}_x , and there is a problem of how \mathbf{m}_x should be chosen. These subjective uncertainties are described by using an interval of possibility:

$$\mathbf{m}_x \in [\bar{\mathbf{x}}(1 - \mathbf{a}_x), \bar{\mathbf{x}}(1 - \mathbf{b}_x)] \quad (19)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ is the estimator of the mean values. A probability of failure is needed in a decision model. One possibility is to maximize the failure probability, i.e. by minimizing the first order reliability index:

$$\bar{\beta}_k = \min [\beta_k(\mathbf{m}_x)] \quad (20)$$

Failure probabilities of layers evaluated by FORM by using equation (17) can be used in equation (12) to estimate the probability of failure of the laminate.

Reliability index computation

Several optimization algorithms are available for estimating the first order reliability index β_k [10], and software performs this calculation [11,12]. The algorithms generally used are the sequential quadratic programming method [13], the gradient projection method [14] and the modified HL-RF method [3,15]. To take uncertainties on the mean values, we have developed a hybrid method, which combines evolutionary computation techniques with deterministic procedures. Evolutionary computation techniques [16,17,18,19,20] are stochastic optimization methods; they are conveniently presented using the metaphor of natural evolution. A randomly initialized population of individuals (set of points of the search space at hand) evolves using a crude parallel of the Darwinian principle of the survival of the fittest (how well they perform with respect to the optimization problem at hand). New individuals are generated using simulated genetic operations such as crossover and mutation. The probability of survival of the newly generated solutions depends on their fitness. The best, with a high probability, are kept, the worst are rapidly discarded.

The whole optimization process is divided into two separate phases. During the first phase, an evolutionary algorithm minimizes the function $\mathbf{g}_k(\alpha r)$, where r is a constant. After the determination of this phase, the second phase of the optimization algorithm is applied to the best solution found during the first phase; this phase iterates until $\mathbf{g}_k(\alpha r) = 0$, where α is a constant. A cycle of this may proceed as follows:

- (1) Choose an initial hypersphere r_0 and set $i = 0$
- (2) Compute $\bar{\alpha}$ such as $\mathbf{g}_k(\bar{\alpha} r_i) = \min [\mathbf{g}_k(\alpha r_i)]$ using an evolutionary method
- (3) Calculate r_{i+1} such as $\mathbf{g}_k(\bar{\alpha} r_{i+1}) = 0$ using a deterministic method
- (4) If $r_{i+1} - r_i \geq \varepsilon$, set r_i to r_{i+1} , $i = i + 1$, and return to (2)
- (5) $\bar{\beta}_k = r_{i+1}$, STOP

DESIGN OPTIMIZATION OF LAMINATE PIPES $\pm\varphi$

Optimization problem

Superior strength, low weight and corrosion resistance justifies the use of composite materials for transferring fluids. For economic reasons, the reinforcing material is often glass ; and resin is usually of the thermosetting type. Since an epoxy matrix absorbs water slowly [21,22,23], epoxy reinforced by glass fibers is often the material chosen. It is the type of laminate which we have chosen to optimize. The winding angle φ and number of plies N are the two major parameters determining the mechanical performance and the economical cost respectively. Design optimization relates mainly to these two parameters.

Fig. 3: Laminate coordinate system

The laminate under study (Fig. 3) is subjected to pressure P and composed of N plies, each of equal thickness e . The volume fraction of R-glass fibers is 69%. Its middle radius r is much greater than its thickness h and its internal radius is $R = 3$ cm. Taking into account the thin cylinder hypothesis and assuming the cylinder is subjected to a close-ended stress (ratio of axial to circumferential stresses $S = 1:2$), only $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ and $\sigma_{zz} = \sigma_{\theta\theta}/2$ can be considered as significant stresses. Assuming the laminate is orthotropic, analysis can be reduced to that of a symmetric laminate. For plane stress, 6 basic physical variables are considered random and uncertain. Their mean values and their intervals of possibilities, coefficients of variation (CV), and laws of probability are summarized in Table 1. We considered an interval of possibility for the value of the winding angle of $\varphi \pm 0.5^\circ$ and a negligible standard deviation. The symmetry of the laminates and external loading studied make it possible to omit index φ .

\mathbf{x}	$\bar{\mu}_x$ (estimator)	\mathbf{a}_x (%)	\mathbf{b}_x (%)	CV(%)	law type
E_1 (MPa)	59500	1	1	10	normal
E_2 (MPa)	22500	10	10	10	normal
ν_{12}	0.23	5	5	10	normal
G_{12} (MPa)	9700	10	10	10	normal
Y^c (MPa)	0.003	10	10	10	normal
e (mm)	0.19	0	0	1	normal

Table 1: Vector of random and uncertain physical variables

The entire optimization problem may be stated as: ‘*minimize the number of plies N with respect to the two variables: pressure P and reliability target \bar{P}^f* ’. To solve this problem, an additional stage is added to determine the winding angle effect. We calculate the number of layers necessary according to desired reliability so that the laminate resists the pressure. This can be estimated by solving the system at the design point :

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta} = \frac{Pr}{h}, \quad h = 2(r - R), \quad N = \frac{h}{e} \quad (21)$$

Deterministic analysis

For this analysis, we use the estimators of mean values like parameters of the mechanical model.

Effect of the winding angle

Equation (10) makes it possible to calculate safety margin M according to the winding angle φ and circumferential stress $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$. Results shows that the optimum angle, i.e. the angle which maximizes the safety margin, is constant and equal to 58.2° . Note that this angle is not the traditional 54.75° which is usually obtained with elastic consideration. The same calculation carried out with different reinforcements, whose characteristics are given in [24] does not lead to the same winding angle (Table 2).

fiber	volume of fiber (%)	φ^{opt} ($^\circ$)
R-glass	60	54.3
E-glass	60	54.9
Kevlar	60	53.2
Carbon	60	53.2

Table 2: Optimal winding angle for different reinforcements (epoxy matrix).

Fig. 4 shows the criterion of damage in the stress space for a laminate whose winding angle is 58.2° . The critical circumferential stress for this angle beyond which the laminate is damaged is about 30 MPa.

Fig. 4: Deterministic criterion in the stress space.

Effect of the number of layers

Fig. 5 using equations (21) shows the evolution of the number of layers necessary depending on the pressure. Calculation for 15 bars gives 8 layers.

Fig. 5: Number of plies versus pressure.

Probabilistic analysis

For this analysis, we take into account scatter in the parameters of the mechanical model as well as uncertainties in their mean values.

Effect of the winding angle

Using the algorithm described, the shape of the reliability index versus the winding angle and circumferential stress is computed. The calculation results shows an optimal line of design. There is thus a relationship connecting the optimum winding angle and circumferential stress with reliability. Using these results and equation (17), we can calculate numerically the evolution of the higher level of failure probability versus circumferential stress for the optimal line (Fig. 6) and the optimum winding angle for the reliability target generally used (Fig. 7). For example, if the reliability target is 10^{-6} , the optimum winding angle is 62° and the circumferential stress limit is about 18.5 MPa.

Fig. 6: Circumferential stress versus reliability target.

Fig. 7: Choice of the winding angle versus reliability target.

Effect of the number of layers

Here, the objective is to calculate the minimum number of plies which check the level of reliability desired for a given pressure. For this calculation, we use equations (21) at the design point.

Fig. 8: Number of plies versus pressure and reliability target

Fig. 8 makes it possible to choose the number of layers of the laminate. For a reliability target of 10^{-6} and one pressure of 15 bars, 14 layers are necessary. The comparison between deterministic analysis and probabilistic analysis, for the same pressure shows a very significant difference in the choice of the number of layers. The difference is 6.

CONCLUSION

We have presented a mechanical analysis of damage behavior in order to determine the failure criterion. It is clear that other criteria can be used, such as rupture or a state of damage. We chose the damage behavior criterion because it targets safety. The algorithm in the probabilistic method used to compute the probability of failure is original. Its main advantage compared to the traditional algorithm is that it takes into account not only randomness, but also subjective uncertainties inherent in composite materials.

This method for the design of laminates means recourse to arbitrary safety coefficients is avoided. It must now be extended to complex mechanical models taking viscous phenomena into account.

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